

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

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Institute of Hotel Management and Tourism

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABDUL SINAN bearing USN4SU20HM201 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Fifth Semester of the B.SC- HM programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABHISHEK EZEKIEL GUNDMI bearing USN4SU20HM202 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Fifth Semester of the B.SC- HM programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABITH KUMAR G bearing USN4SU20HM203 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Fifth Semester of the B.SC- HM programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms AJAY U bearing USN4SU20HM204 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Fifth Semester of the B.SC- HM programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms GURUPRASAD bearing USN4SU20HM205 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Fifth Semester of the B.SC- HM programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms HEISNAM UTOPRIYARI DEVI bearing USN4SU20HM206 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Fifth Semester of the B.SC- HM programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms IARISALANG SWETT bearing USN4SU20HM207 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Fifth Semester of the B.SC- HM programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms JINS GOLDIA bearing USN4SU20HM208 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Fifth Semester of the B.SC- HM programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms JITHESH bearing USN4SU20HM209 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Fifth Semester of the B.SC- HM programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms JITHU T R bearing USN4SU20HM210 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Fifth Semester of the B.SC- HM programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MANOJ KUMAR M bearing USN4SU20HM212 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Fifth Semester of the B.SC- HM programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MAYUR PRASAD NAIR bearing USN4SU20HM213 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Fifth Semester of the B.SC- HM programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MOHAMMED MUSTHAFA bearing USN4SU20HM214 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Fifth Semester of the B.SC- HM programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MOHAMMED THANSEEF bearing USN4SU20HM215 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Fifth Semester of the B.SC- HM programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SAM BIJU bearing USN4SU20HM216 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Fifth Semester of the B.SC- HM programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SANDESH bearing USN4SU20HM217 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Fifth Semester of the B.SC- HM programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHETTY MEGHA SHIVANAND bearing USN4SU20HM218 has completed his/her Roaster duty at Hotel Srinivas & Hotel Saffron in the Fifth Semester of the B.SC- HM programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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